

1 **Combatting intracellular pathogens using bacteriophage delivery**

2 Avijit Goswami¹, Pallavi Raj Sharma¹, Rachit Agarwal^{1#}

3 ¹ Centre for BioSystems Science and Engineering, Indian Institute of Science, Bengaluru,
4 India

5 #Corresponding author

6 Address correspondence to Rachit Agarwal, rachit@iisc.ac.in

8 **Abstract**

9 Intracellular pathogens reside in specialized compartments within the host cells
10 restricting the access of antibiotics. Insufficient intracellular delivery of antibiotics
11 along with several other resistance mechanisms weaken the efficacy of current
12 therapies. An alternative to antibiotic therapy could be bacteriophage (phage)
13 therapy. Although phage therapy has been in practice for a century against various
14 bacterial infections, the efficacy of phages against intracellular bacteria is still being
15 explored. In this review, we will discuss the advancement and challenges in phage
16 therapy, particularly against intracellular bacterial pathogens. Finally, we will highlight
17 the uptake mechanisms and approaches to overcome the challenges to phage
18 therapy against intracellular bacteria.

19 **Keywords:** Antibiotic resistance, Phage uptake, Intracellular phage delivery, Particle
20 engineering

21 **Abbreviations:** MRSA: methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, PLGA: poly
22 (lactic-co-glycolic) acid, CPP: cell-penetrating peptides

23 **1. Introduction**

24 Several bacterial pathogens have developed strategies to survive within a
25 mammalian host cell and are known as intracellular bacteria. These pathogens
26 modulate the intracellular environment, create a suitable niche, and bypass the harsh
27 consequences of encountering the host immune system. Intracellular bacteria can be
28 classified as obligate, which are unable to grow outside a host cell like *Chlamydia*
29 *trachomatis* (*C. trachomatis*) and *Coxiella burnetii*, or facultative, which can grow
30 outside and inside a host cell for e.g. *Salmonella enterica* (*S. enterica*),
31 *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (*M. tuberculosis*) and *Listeria monocytogenes* (*L.*
32 *monocytogenes*) [1-4]. These pathogens account for high mortality in humans. About
33 1.4 million patients succumbed to tuberculosis in 2019 [5]. In 2015, 90,300 deaths
34 occurred from non-typhoidal salmonellosis and about 178,000 people died of
35 typhoidal salmonellosis [6]. Additionally, other pathogens like *Staphylococcus aureus*
36 (*S. aureus*), *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*)
37 can also invade and survive within host cells [7-9].

38 A major challenge for treatment intracellular bacteria is the inability of many
39 antibacterial agents to cross the mammalian cell membrane barrier [10]. The rising
40 concern over antibiotic resistance demands novel treatment approaches. Phages
41 are viruses that infect and lyse specific host bacteria and their application as
42 therapeutics is termed as phage therapy. There is a large reservoir of around 10^{31} -
43 10^{32} phages in the biosphere, which could be tapped in, to solve the challenge of
44 antimicrobial resistance [11,12]. Multiple review articles on phage therapy have been
45 published recently [13-16], however, to our knowledge, only a few review articles
46 have exclusively focused on developing new strategies to deliver phages for targeting
47 intracellular pathogens [17,18]. In this review, we have primarily discussed the

48 advancement in phage therapy to control intracellular pathogens. We have also
49 highlighted pertinent challenges and possible solutions for phage therapy to tackle
50 intracellular bacterial infections.

51 **2. Intracellular bacteria**

52 Intracellular bacterial pathogens are classified in facultative if able to grow either
53 inside or outside a host cell or obligate if unable to grow outside a host cell.
54 Intracellular pathogens have the inherent ability to cross the mammalian cell
55 membrane via multiple mechanisms [19,20]. These pathogens can penetrate and
56 localize in both phagocytic (for instance, macrophages) and non-phagocytic (for
57 instance, endothelial/epithelial cells) hosts [21]. Organisms like *Mycobacterium*
58 utilizes the natural phagocytic ability of the macrophages to invade via receptor
59 mediated endocytosis and reside within them [22,23]. On the other hand, pathogens
60 like *C. trachomatis*, *S. aureus*, and *Shigella* have specialized mechanisms to induce
61 cytoskeletal reorientation that generates phagocytic activity in non-phagocytic
62 epithelial cells [24-27]. Unlike these pathogens which can invade specific cell type,
63 *Salmonella* has the ability to infect both the macrophages and the non-phagocytic
64 epithelial cells. These pathogens utilize several mechanisms of cellular entry (**Table**
65 **1**). Some pathogens like *Listeria* and *Yersinia* have surface proteins that binds to
66 specific host cell receptor and induces a signalling cascade event that facilitates
67 clathrin mediated endocytosis (Zipper mode) [28,29]. Alternatively, pathogens like
68 *Salmonella* and *Shigella* utilizes its type 3 secretion system to translocate effector
69 molecules into the host cell that triggers actin rich membrane ruffles necessary for
70 endocytosis (Trigger mode) [30,31]. Both mechanisms are extremely crucial to
71 infiltrate non-phagocytic epithelial cells.

72 Upon internalization, these pathogens reside within specialized intracellular
73 compartments known as phagosomes and/or endosomes (**Fig 1**). In phagocytes,
74 these phagosomes are destined to lysosomal fusion, where the low pH and
75 degradative enzymes destroy the pathogens. However, most of these intracellular
76 pathogens have evolved strategies to block phago-lysosomal fusion and subvert the
77 harsh bactericidal environment within the lysosomes. Interestingly, some pathogens
78 can escape from the phagosomes and survive in the cytoplasm [8,32] (**Fig 1**). For
79 instance, *M. tuberculosis* arrests phago-lysosomal fusion and even survives in the
80 cytoplasm and lysosomes, thus creating a diverse niche for its survival within
81 macrophages [4,33]. *S. aureus* can survive and replicate within the phago-lysosomes
82 in a low pH condition [34]. These diverse mechanisms employed by the pathogens to
83 reside within the target cell create additional limitations for the current treatment
84 strategies.

85

86 **Fig 1: Intracellular sites where the pathogens reside.** Intracellular bacteria reside at
 87 specialized locations within the host mammalian cell. These sites include (1) the
 88 endosome/phagosome, (2) the phago-lysosomal compartment, or (3) the cytoplasm.

89 **3. Drawbacks of antibiotics to curtail intracellular bacterial infection**

90 The effectiveness of an antibacterial agent depends on its local concentration, which
 91 should be sustained at a therapeutic level to eliminate the pathogen. Exposure to a
 92 suboptimal dose of antibiotics leads to the selection of drug-resistant bacteria or the
 93 development of a tolerant phenotype [35]. Some of the hurdles that encountered
 94 during antibiotic treatment while targeting intracellular pathogens are illustrated in
 95 **figure 2.**

96 Drugs like macrolides and quinolones are readily taken up by phagocytic cells.
97 Despite the intracellular accumulation of antibiotics, efflux pumps present on
98 mammalian surface and endosomal membranes, like P-glycoproteins and multidrug
99 resistance proteins [36], lower the intracellular drug concentration within a host cell
100 [37,38]. This hampers the local intracellular concentration required for killing the
101 pathogen. For example, reduced intracellular activity of several antibiotics like
102 fluoroquinolones, macrolides, streptogramins, lincosamides and rifampicin was
103 observed against *L. monocytogenes* in multidrug resistant protein 1 overexpressed
104 carcinoma cell line [39]. P-glycoprotein inhibitors (verapamil, ciclosporin, and GF
105 120918) and multidrug resistance protein inhibitors (gemfibrozil or probenecid) were
106 shown to be effective in increasing the intracellular accumulation of the antibiotics in
107 mammalian cells; however, disparate effects of various inhibitors are observed and
108 their efficacy is dependent on the antibiotics used [40-42].

109 Apart from intracellular drug concentration, subcellular localisation of bacteria also
110 governs the efficacy of antibiotics [43-45]. Some pathogens like *S. aureus* and *M.*
111 *tuberculosis* have an inherent ability to survive within the phago-lysosomal
112 compartment with a low pH condition of 4.5-5.0. Maintaining the activity of
113 antibacterial agents at such a low pH is another challenge [46,47].

114 Stress induced by antibiotics and host oxidative response can cause the
115 transformation of bacteria into a non-replicating metabolic state, known as persisters
116 [48,49]. Numerous bacteria like *M. tuberculosis*, *P. aeruginosa*, *Salmonella* and *S.*
117 *aureus* can persist in a growth arrested state with reduced metabolism which results
118 in high tolerance to antibiotics over a long period of time [50]. For example,
119 internalization of *S. typhimurium* within the macrophage vacuolar environment
120 induces phenotypic heterogeneity that results in the formation of non-replicating

121 persister cells [51]. Wayne and Sohaskey had extensively discussed the non-
122 replicating nature of *M. tuberculosis* within the host that causes latent infections that
123 are often resistant to conventional treatment [52]. Although there are alternative
124 approaches like intermittent drug doses to target persisters, these have not been
125 widely explored in clinics [53] (**Fig 2**). Phagocytes produce reactive nitrogen and
126 oxygen species as a response to invading pathogens [54]. The antimicrobial function
127 of reactive oxygen species (ROS) has been well documented in killing intracellular
128 pathogens and inducing signaling events to trigger an inflammatory response [55].
129 Interestingly, recent studies have reported that the consequence of respiratory burst
130 leading to ROS production failed to kill intracellular pathogens like *S. aureus* and was
131 shown to induce tolerance to multiple antibiotics [56]. Similarly, connection between
132 ROS and antibiotic tolerance has been established in *M. marinum* where intracellular
133 ROS resulted in increased expression of drug efflux pump [57,58]. Although not
134 experimentally proven, another explanation could be DNA mutagenesis caused by
135 ROS exposure leading to physical damage to the genetic material [59,60]. Error-
136 prone polymerase activity in response to the stress induced by respiratory burst might
137 lead to random mutations causing antibiotic resistance or tolerance [61,62]. (**Fig 3**).

138

139 **Fig 2: Drawbacks of antibiotics against intracellular pathogens.** A schematic
 140 representation that depicts the multidimensional shortcomings of antibiotics against
 141 intracellular infection.

142 **4. Advances in phage therapy to combat intracellular pathogens**

143 Phage therapy is emerging as a last-resort treatment for patients with antibiotic-
 144 resistant infections. In a recent report, Dedrick et al. showed that phage therapy could
 145 be used for treating disseminated drug-resistant *M. abscessus* infection in a young
 146 cystic fibrosis patient [63]. A cocktail of genetically engineered phage effectively
 147 cleared *M. abscessus* infection when delivered intravenously and led to wound closure
 148 and resolution of infected skin nodules [63].

149 For phages to be effective against intracellular infections, they need to reach the
 150 intracellular site where the bacteria reside. The studies on intracellular phage delivery

151 can be grouped into two categories - free phage delivery and carrier-mediated delivery
152 of phages.

153 **4.1 Free Phage delivery**

154 Within their host, intracellular pathogens are shielded from numerous effector
155 molecules and cells due to the protective semi-permeable plasma membrane. Phages
156 are high molecular weight molecules (> 10 megadaltons) that are unable to passively
157 diffuse across the plasma membrane. However, there are several mechanisms that
158 can be utilized by phages to overcome this biological barrier. The possibility of phage
159 interaction and transport through mammalian cells became evident in the early 1970s
160 when high doses of phages against *V. cholerae* were administered orally for the
161 treatment of diarrhea in humans and about 10^2 pfu/mL phages were observed in the
162 blood throughout treatment duration [64]. Similarly, phages have been found in
163 different organs after intravenous delivery. Recently, a phage mixture was
164 administered intravenously for the treatment of a patient with disseminated drug
165 resistant *M. abscessus*, and a substantially high titer of phages was detected in
166 sputum and feces, in addition to serum [63]. Phages have also been detected in the
167 brain tissue after intranasal delivery [65] and even fetal tissue after systemic
168 administration [66]. Nguyen et al. demonstrated rapid transcytosis of phage T4 from
169 apical to basolateral chambers in a variety of cells like Madin-Darby Canine Kidney
170 (MDCK) cells, T84 cells (colon epithelial), Caco-2 cells (colon epithelial), A549 cells
171 (lung epithelial), Huh7 cells (hepatocyte epithelial cell-like), and hBMec cells (brain
172 endothelial) [67]. It was suggested that phages traffic through the Golgi apparatus.
173 Phage UAB_Phi20 was also shown to be transcytosed across Caco-2 cells and
174 human colon tumorigenic (HT-29) cells [68]. In addition to transcytosis, phages have
175 been reported to utilize phagocytosis, endocytosis and pinocytosis to enter

176 mammalian cells (**Fig 3**). Phagocytosis is carried out by professional phagocytes,
177 usually immune cells such as monocytes, macrophages, and dendritic cells. These
178 cells can engulf invading bacteria, particles, or cell debris and eventually degrade them
179 in lysosomes. Endocytosis is a constitutive process carried out by all mammalian cells
180 for the uptake of nutrients and small molecules. Clathrin and caveolae-mediated
181 endocytosis are two major types of endocytosis, among others, observed in
182 mammalian cells. Pinocytosis involves uptake of large amounts of extracellular fluid,
183 which is also a constitutive process in mammalian cells. For instance, phages can be
184 engineered to enable penetration through the gut. The peptide YPRLLTP (identified
185 by *in vivo* bio-panning protocol) displayed on the capsid of M13 phages facilitated
186 translocation across the intestinal lining [69].

187 Phage interaction with mammalian cells for therapeutic implications has been
188 extensively reviewed [70,71]. Tian et al. showed that in HeLa cells and MCF-7 breast
189 cancer cells, M13 enters through clathrin-mediated endocytosis and micropinocytosis
190 [72], while it uses caveolae-mediated endocytosis for human dermal microvascular
191 endothelial cells. The internalization efficiency of M13 phage was enhanced several
192 log folds by genetically modifying the phages to display cell-penetrating domains 3D8
193 VL transbody or TAT peptide [73]. These modifications resulted in different modes of
194 phage internalization and fate as they interact with distinct cell surface
195 glycosaminoglycans. 3D8 VL-M13 utilized the caveolae-mediated endocytosis and
196 remained stable after internalization for more than 18 h in the cytosol. TAT modified
197 phage was mainly internalized via clathrin and caveolae-mediated endocytosis and
198 were found in multiple subcellular compartments and were degraded in lysosomes
199 within 2 h of internalization. Overall, this report focuses on the efficiency rates at which

200 engineered M13 displaying various peptides can be delivered into the mammalian
201 cells [73].

202 Phage opsonisation by serum proteins can trigger phagocytosis [74]. Møller-Olsen et
203 al. showed internalization of fluorescently labelled phage K1F-GFP into human urinary
204 bladder epithelial cells via phagocytosis [75]. These phages were successful in killing
205 both extracellular and intracellular *E. coli* EV36-RFP infection in T24 urinary epithelial
206 cells. The authors used a SYTOX dead cell stain and estimated the co-localization of
207 SYTOX with *E. coli* RFP using confocal microscopy. Phage treatment showed 77%
208 co-localization compared to 29% in untreated samples [75].

209 Zhang et al. showed endocytosis and accumulation of *S. aureus* phage
210 vB_SauM_JS25 in non-phagocytic MAC-T bovine epithelial cells over time [76].
211 Microscopic evaluation showed that about 12% of cells were positive for phages. A
212 time-dependent intracellular killing (1-1.5 log order reduction in 12 h) of *S. aureus* by
213 phage vB_SauM_JS25 was observed in MAC-T bovine epithelial cells. The
214 extracellular bacteria was eliminated by adding lysostaphin (20 µg/ml) 1h after
215 infection [76].

216 Lehti et al. described that endocytic uptake of *E. coli* PK1A2 phage into live eukaryotic
217 neuroblastoma cells is dependent on the presence of polysialic acid residues on the
218 mammalian cell surface [77]. The phages show initial adsorption to the polysaccharide
219 receptor which enabled uptake. Phage adsorption and internalization were lower when
220 there was less sialic acid on the cell surface or when sialic acid was added separately
221 as a competitive binding site. Many internalized phages (~30%) were found to be
222 active even after 24 h. The phages eventually localized to the lysosome and became
223 undetectable in 48 h [77].

224 Peng et al. showed that free mycobacteriophage D29, a lytic phage, significantly
225 reduced the intracellular *M. tuberculosis* count in peritoneal macrophage cells [78].
226 Mouse peritoneal macrophages were infected with *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv for 4 h
227 followed by washing for three times with Hank's buffered salt solution (HBSS) to
228 remove all extracellular bacteria. Phages treatment were given for 24 h and 48h post-
229 infection. Compared to the control group (no phage treatment), a high dose of phages
230 (2.0×10^7 pfu/well) effectively lowered the viable intracellular bacterial count by 76%
231 after 24 h and 92% after 48 h [78]. Additionally, Lapenkova et al. investigated the effect
232 of D29 on the mouse macrophages infected with virulent mycobacterial strain H37Rv
233 [79]. Phage D29 (10^8 pfu) was incubated with infected macrophages for 24 h, followed
234 by washing and re-incubation with fresh D29 for another 24 h. Intracellular bacteria
235 (H37Rv) were plated after disrupting the infected macrophage membrane by two
236 freeze/thaw cycle and allowed to grow from 3 weeks. Results depicted a 10-fold
237 reduction in CFU counts in phage treated samples compared to control samples [79].
238 Promising results were also observed against other opportunistic intracellular
239 pathogens like *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. Capparelli and group documented that *in vitro*
240 phage (M^{Sa}) treatment of intracellular *S. aureus* infected peritoneal macrophages
241 resulted in 70% reduction in CFU [80]. To check for efficacy of M^{Sa} against local
242 infection, *S. aureus* was administered subcutaneously followed by M^{Sa} treatment 4
243 days later. Phage treatment resulted in a 2-log fold reduction in bacterial CFUs
244 compared to untreated group and led to 97% survival of mice infected with lethal doses
245 of *S. aureus* A170 strain. Although in *in vivo* studies, there was no direct evidence
246 about whether the phages were effective against extracellular or intracellular bacteria
247 [80]. The authors further showed a significant role of the phage in controlling

248 Methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) infection (100% survival of mice treated with
249 10^9 pfu/mice compared to 20% survival in the untreated group) [80].

250 Phage therapy against facultative intracellular pathogen *Burkholderia pseudomallei*
251 was successful both *in vitro* and *in vivo* [81]. When phage C34 was added prior to
252 infection, the survival rate of *B. pseudomallei* infected lung epithelial cells (A549 cell
253 line) increased by 2-fold *in vitro*. However, no significant effect was observed when
254 the phage was delivered post-infection. The authors further showed that pre-treatment
255 (24 h before infection) and post-treatment (2 h after infection) also protected (33%
256 survival compared to no survival in untreated) the intranasally infected (*B.*
257 *pseudomallei*) mice which highlights the prophylactic and therapeutic potential of
258 phages. Nevertheless, no direct evidence of reducing intracellular bacterial load was
259 documented *in vivo* [81]. Similar study in support of prophylactic ability of phage
260 treatment has been reported for *M. tuberculosis* infection using D29 phage [82]. C57
261 black mice were exposed to aerosolized phages ($7.7 \pm 0.3 \log_{10}$ PFU/mouse) 30 mins
262 prior to 50-100 CFU of *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv. Compared to untreated mice, 70%
263 reduction in CFU count was observed in phage treated animals after 24 h of infection
264 [82]. Kolenda et al. reported that in uninfected cells, only ~100 pfu/mL were recovered
265 from the osteoblasts after 24 h of incubation with free phages (10^7 - 10^9 pfu/mL) while
266 in *S. aureus* infected osteoblasts, 10^6 - 10^7 pfu/mL of phages were recovered indicating
267 that phage entry into the osteoblasts was dependent on re-infecting bacteria and the
268 phages were proliferating within the bacteria. This was supported by co-incubation
269 with vancomycin and rifampin that reduced the extracellular re-infecting bacteria and
270 resulted in only $\sim 10^3$ pfu/mL present intracellularly [83]. Detailed investigation in this
271 study revealed that phages could get internalized only after adsorbing to the re-
272 infecting bacteria however they were ineffective in reducing intracellular CFU despite

273 internalization. This lack of efficacy could be either loss of the phage activity in the
 274 intracellular environment or induction of bacterial dormancy within osteoblasts which
 275 may have inhibited propagation of phages. However, no evidence was provided in the
 276 study to clarify these speculations. Studies which have discussed free phage delivery
 277 for intracellular pathogens have been summarized in Table 2.

278 To improve therapeutic outcomes for intracellular infections, it is essential to enhance
 279 phage uptake by infected cells and target the intracellular bacteria.

280

281 **Fig 3: Mechanism of phage uptake.** The illustration depicts various modes of intracellular
 282 uptake of free phages or carrier mediated phages.

283 **4.2 Carrier Mediated Phage delivery**

284 Although free phage therapy is effective in some instances, as mentioned above, there
 285 is a need to improve the delivery of the phages intracellularly. This can be achieved

286 by a “Trojan horse” approach that involves encapsulation or loading of phages onto
287 carriers. Studies on carrier mediated phage therapy have been summarized in Table
288 3. Broxmeyer et al. reported a novel strategy of phage delivery via non-pathogenic
289 strain *M. smegmatis* infected with phage TM4 [84]. Neither *M. smegmatis* alone nor
290 phage TM4 treatment alone affected intracellular *M. tuberculosis* and *M. avium* count
291 within RAW 264.7 cells. Interestingly, TM4 infected *M. smegmatis* was phagocytosed
292 and colocalized with *M. avium* containing vacuole after internalization. This resulted in
293 an approximately 100-fold reduction in the bacterial load after 48 h of treatment *in vitro*
294 [84]. The results were further validated *in vivo* by Danelishvili et al. to treat
295 disseminated *M. avium* infection using phage TM4 adsorbed on *M. smegmatis* that
296 accounted for significant reduction in bacterial load in the spleen. Although significant,
297 direct evidence of phage mediated intracellular bacterial killing was not presented in
298 animal model [85]. The idea of vectorization proposed by Broxmeyer and group [84]
299 ensured the delivery of active phage to the target site after subcutaneous
300 administration. While innovative, the administration of live bacteria in patients is risky
301 for patients. The use of biomaterials such as liposomes and polymeric particles can
302 provide a suitable alternative for clinical translation as several such systems are
303 already clinically approved (such as AmBisome and Doxil) [86,87]. A few approaches
304 have been developed to encapsulate phages in liposomes and polymers [88,89]. For
305 instance, 100 nm cationic liposome-encapsulated phages, KPO1K2, (average phage
306 size of ~ 50nm) formulated by conventional approach (lipid thin film hydration) ensured
307 effective intracellular delivery inside *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (*K. pneumoniae*) infected
308 macrophages [90]. Gentamicin was added to the culture media to kill any extracellular
309 bacteria and only focus on intracellular bacteria. The authors reported that cationic
310 liposomes carrying phages caused 94.6% killing of intracellular *K. pneumoniae*

311 compared to free phages which accounted for 21% killing after 24 h [90]. In addition,
312 liposome-encapsulated phages were also shown to be protected against neutralizing
313 antibodies compared to free phages [90]. Another group reported that intraperitoneal
314 delivery of liposome-encapsulated phage cocktails was effective against *K.*
315 *pneumoniae* infected burn wounds in BALB/c mice model [91]. In this study, phage
316 entrapped liposomes with an average diameter of 229 nm showed an encapsulation
317 efficiency of $79.2 \pm 5.6\%$. After 72 h of treatment, liposome entrapped phage cocktail
318 showed 1-2 log order reduction in bacterial counts compared to free phages in skin,
319 blood, and liver. Although the phage activity on killing intracellular bacteria couldn't be
320 established from the *in vivo* experiment [91].

321 Along with liposomes, nanocrystals and polymers can also serve as an efficient tool
322 for phage encapsulation and delivery [92-94] (**Fig 4**). Fulgione et al. reported that
323 biomimetic hydroxyapatite (HA) nanocrystals effectively delivered *Salmonella* phage
324 (SR ϕ 1) intracellularly [95]. HepG2 cells were infected with 10^8 CFU/mL of *S. enterica*
325 serovar Rissen followed by treatment with free SR ϕ 1 (10^7 PFU/mL), only HA
326 nanocrystals or equivalent phage-loaded HA nanocrystals for 24 h. Intracellular CFU
327 count revealed reduced count of 10^5 CFU/ml for HA-SR ϕ 1 compared to 10^8 CFU/ml
328 in free phage and only HA group. Extracellular bacteria was eliminated by using
329 gentamicin for 3 h post infection. The authors also confirmed enhanced stability of
330 HA-SR ϕ 1 at pH 4.0 compared to free phages suggesting a potential use of such
331 mineral crystals at low pH conditions like phagolysosomes [95].

332 Overall, these studies suggest that the use of carrier-mediated delivery systems in the
333 form of liposomes or polymers can be utilized for efficient intracellular phage delivery.

334

335 **Figure 4: Various phage delivery technologies.** Multiple encapsulation and delivery
 336 techniques have been implemented to increase the stability and intracellular delivery
 337 of phages.

338 **5. Challenges towards intracellular phage therapy**

339 While phage therapy holds the potential to tackle intracellular bacterial infections,
 340 several challenges constrain their translation into clinics. Apart from the usual
 341 challenges for translation of phage therapy for extracellular bacteria such as bacterial
 342 defence mechanisms (CRISPR/CAS machinery, restriction-modification system) [96-
 343 99], bacterial accessibility [100] and phage stability in in-vivo conditions [101], there
 344 are several other challenges for intracellular phage therapy. Intracellular bacteria can
 345 develop resistance against phage infection by multiple mechanisms. When these
 346 pathogens establish infection intracellularly, they encounter multiple environmental
 347 stresses such as nutrition deprivation, hypoxia, or changes in pH [102]. Such

348 conditions can induce a state of dormancy and render the bacteria metabolically
349 inactive, thus preventing phage amplification and cell lysis [103]. Studies on phage
350 infection on bacteria under dormant, acidic, and hypoxic growth conditions are limited.
351 It was shown by Swift et al. that phage D29 was not effective in lysing the bacterial
352 host *M. smegmatis* in a hypoxic environment [104]. On the contrary, some studies
353 have reported successful phage infection in stationary phase host bacteria [105,106].
354 A recent study has reported that a cocktail of phages was effective in inhibiting *M.*
355 *smegmatis* growth under acidic, hypoxic and stationary phase growth conditions [107].
356 Such investigations are critical for designing phage formulations that will be effective
357 in lysing bacteria in their intracellular niche. In addition, stress conditions can trigger
358 the production of outer membrane vesicles that carry phage receptors and can act as
359 a decoy and bind phage while the host bacteria remains unaffected [108,109].
360 Intracellular pathogens may also be sequestered in vacuoles and phages may not be
361 able to target such infections.

362 It is evident that the occurrence of phage-resistance is inevitable and thus bacterial
363 susceptibility testing is critical before initiation of therapy. Unfortunately, resistance
364 can also emerge during treatment. The application of a phage cocktail is suggested to
365 mitigate the problem. Unlike antibiotics, there are numerous lytic phages for most
366 bacterial species that can be used to form phage mixtures and overcome resistance.
367 Phage resistance can emerge if the bacteria modify its cell surface receptor and blocks
368 attachment of phages. It is expected that similar to extracellular bacteria, use of phage
369 cocktails would decrease the probability that bacteria would develop resistance
370 against all the phages at once. Hence, rational designing of a phage cocktail,
371 identification of bacterial receptors targeted by each phage becomes imperative to
372 design phage cocktails that target diverse bacterial receptors. This would ensure that

373 the evolving phage-resistant population will still be susceptible to other phages in the
374 cocktail [110-112]. A phage cocktail was shown to reduce development of phage
375 tolerance in *M. smegmatis* and *M. tuberculosis* compared to treatment with single
376 phages [107]. Broad-range lytic phages need to be identified or developed and tested
377 against clinical strains and demographically predominant strains in addition to lab
378 strains [113-115]. Synergy between phages and antibiotics is a widely reported for
379 extracellular bacteria [116]. The combinatorial effect of phages along with antibiotics
380 has been investigated in multiple opportunistic pathogens like *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *K.*
381 *pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii* and *Enterococcus faecalis* (extensively
382 reviewed in [14,117]). However, there is need to study phage-antibiotic synergy in
383 context of intracellular bacteria as it could pave way for combinatorial treatment to
384 prevent rapid rise in resistance against phages and antibiotics.

385 The host defence mechanism can exert additional barrier to the circulating phages
386 and influence the pharmacokinetics depending on the route of administration. Immune
387 response can act on phages both by innate and adaptive response. Innate responses
388 include complement mediated lysis or opsonization of phages, and eventual
389 phagocytosis and degradation by mononuclear phagocyte system (MPS) [118].
390 Phages are mostly found in liver or spleen after intravenous delivery which harbours
391 most of the MPS cells [119]. Antibody production against phages has also been
392 reported that can reduce efficacy of phage therapy [118,119]. Kim et al. showed that
393 attachment of hydrophilic polymers, such as polyethylene glycol, to phages increases
394 the half-life while in circulation and decreases susceptibility to innate and adaptive
395 immune response [120]. Carrier mediated delivery of phages as discussed above
396 could also modulate the adaptive immune response but needs to be further tested
397 [90,121]

398 In addition, engineering approaches such as synthetic biology-based phage
399 modification, development of chimeric phages that exhibit strong lytic activity [122,123]
400 and biomaterial-based delivery can significantly improve the performance of the phage
401 formulation by enhancing uptake by infected cells and targeting the intracellular niche
402 as discussed before [124-126].

403 Several phase 1 trials with phages have been conducted which validate the safety of
404 the formulation in healthy volunteers. A list of clinical trials utilizing phages for therapy
405 has been tabulated (**Table 4**). It is expected that the results of these trials would pave
406 the way for bringing phage therapy into regular clinical practice.

407 **6. Future strategies for phage targeting to intracellular bacteria**

408 Despite the advances in the application of phage as a potential therapeutic agent
409 against bacterial pathogens, additional refinements are necessary to ensure
410 sustainability. Some of the major questions that need to be addressed are in terms of
411 the delivery of phages at the site of infection. Since intracellular pathogens are
412 generally present inside specialized vesicles within a host cell, new strategies must
413 be designed for intracellular trafficking of phages/particles to various subcellular sites
414 like phagosomes, phagolysosomes, or some escaping from these vacuoles to the
415 cytoplasm. Chemical conjugation of peptides or administration of small molecules
416 along with phage carrying particles for enhanced uptake can be an innovative
417 strategy to deliver them into the specific subcellular sites. Effective uptake of phage
418 particles can be facilitated by cell-penetrating peptides (CPP). Apart from
419 endocytosis, CPPs are directly translocated by toroidal pore and barrel stave pore
420 formation (detailed uptake mechanism reviewed elsewhere) [127,128]. These
421 features of CPPs evade endosomal or vesicular trapping and ensure proper targeting
422 of cargos to specific organelles. Hussain et al. conjugated vancomycin-carrying

423 nanoparticles with cyclic 9-amino-acid peptide CARGGLKSC (CARG) that
424 specifically accumulated in staphylococcal infected lung and skin but not in normal
425 uninfected tissues [129]. The peptide targets bacterial surface components as was
426 observed by *in vitro* labelling. Infected mice treated with intravenous injections of the
427 CARG-conjugated vancomycin particles (one-day post-infection) showed 100%
428 recovery and long-term survival [129]. Engineered nanoparticles with specific homing
429 peptides ensured targeted delivery into the intracellular niche harboring the pathogen.
430 Additionally, genetically modified phages expressing certain peptide sequences on
431 their outer surface can facilitate the uptake process and organellar targeting. By the
432 virtue of protein-ligand interactions, particles can be engineered for targeted delivery
433 using the specific receptors present on the cell surface. For instance, a 2.5-fold
434 increase in cellular uptake was observed with liposomes comprised of 7.5%
435 mannosylated cholesterol compared to bare liposomes in alveolar macrophages
436 [124]. In another report, Yang et al. demonstrated that mannose-functionalized star-
437 shaped antimicrobial polycarbonates were effective compared to control polymer in
438 causing a 3-fold reduction in intracellular *M. bovis* BCG CFU/mL count after 72 h
439 treatment in THP-1 monocytic cells [130]. Use of such ligand functionalized polymer
440 could increase the efficiency of intracellular delivery of phage and should be explored
441 further.

442 Carrier mediated delivery was shown to be more effective in reducing intracellular
443 pathogen as phage internalization by infected cells was enhanced [84,90,131]. There
444 are several methods of achieving high phage encapsulation within various carriers.
445 The cost of the polymers and lipids is low compared to biomolecules and generally
446 encapsulation and purification processes are rapid and can be done in a few hours.
447 Cinquerrui et al. proposed a microfluidics-based nano-encapsulation of phages in

448 sub-micron sized liposomes using phospholipid 1,2-distearoyl-sn-glycero-3-
449 phosphocholine (DSPC) and cholesterol [88]. The size of liposomes could be
450 modulated by varying the concentration of cholesterol and regulating the
451 hydrodynamic conditions. Phage T3 with a diameter of around 65 nm and Phage K
452 with a head of around 80 nm and a tail length of approximately 200nm were used in
453 the study. Interestingly, the compact tail-free head of phage T3 showed higher
454 encapsulation yield compared to phage K [88]. Considering the large size of the
455 mycobacteriophages, Neith et al. bypassed the conventional liposome formulation
456 with alternative approaches by performing rehydration of lipid films by gel-assisted
457 giant unilamellar vesicle formation and inverse emulsion [131]. In gel-assisted vesicle
458 formation, lipid film was rehydrated on dried polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) gel using 10%
459 sucrose solution. In inverse emulsion technique, a step-wise lipid bilayer formation
460 occurs where the inner layer was created by water-in-oil emulsion and was placed on
461 top of another oily lipid solution (outer layer) which was emulsified by titration with a
462 blunt end syringe. In both these techniques, a moderate to high encapsulation
463 efficiency was observed (approx. 50% phage positive vesicles in case of gel-assisted
464 technique and almost 100% phage positive vesicles in case of inverse emulsion
465 technique). Both the techniques resulted in large vesicles of approximately 15-20 μm .
466 Conversely, conventional liposome formulation resulted in particle size of around 5
467 μm but had low encapsulation efficiency compared to the gel-assisted technique. This
468 could be due to large size of phages and low phage concentration used at the time
469 of synthesis. When cell uptake experiments were performed with 5 μm size
470 liposomes, a 4-fold higher uptake was observed in THP-1 macrophage cells
471 compared to the free phages. However, *in vitro* efficacy of the phages in reducing
472 intracellular bacteria was not reported [131].

473 Several studies have successfully shown the use of polymers to develop nanocarriers
474 for intracellular antibiotic delivery which can be adapted towards delivery of phages
475 [132-134]. For instance, polymers like poly (lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA)
476 encapsulated azithromycin enhanced the efficacy of the drug to reduce intracellular
477 *Chlamydia* infection by decreasing the area of inclusion (proportional to infection load)
478 by 50% in lung epithelial cells compared to the free drug [132]. Similarly, particle
479 engineering approaches for intracellular delivery of vancomycin showed specific
480 release at lower pH and enhanced MRSA killing by 5-fold compared to the free drug
481 in J774A.1 macrophages [133]. Such mechanisms will ensure minimal loss of drug
482 while in circulation, thus maintaining an optimal drug concentration only inside
483 pathogen containing vesicles with low pH compared to free drug [113,134,135].
484 Phages can also be encapsulated within PLGA microparticles using a water/oil/water
485 double emulsion process [89]. Phages against *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* were
486 encapsulated with 18% and 27% efficiency respectively within 10 µm polymeric
487 microparticles. Modifications were made to the standard double emulsion process to
488 minimize the interaction of phages with the organic solvent which can cause
489 denaturation. The resultant dry powder formulation of phages had good aerosol
490 properties but a low shelf life [89]. Phage inactivation due to exposure to organic
491 solvents like ethanol, acetonitrile, dimethylsulfoxide, and dimethylformamide hamper
492 the efficacy of the phage-loaded microparticles [136]. Alternative surfactants like
493 polyvinyl alcohol can be employed to improve formulation stability [113]. Additionally,
494 phages can be adsorbed on the particle surface to alleviate concerns of denaturation
495 during the fabrication process. Agarwal et al. showed that a mixture of three to five
496 phages can be adsorbed on polymeric (PLGA) particles [121]. The authors were able
497 to load ~10⁶ phages/mg of particles and phage-particles were effective against

498 *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* cystic fibrosis mice. Phage adsorbed microparticles
499 significantly reduced *P. aeruginosa* infection by 1.5 log fold in cystic fibrosis mice
500 compared free phages [121]. Although these studies have not focused on intracellular
501 phage therapy, they provide technologies that can be adapted and explored against
502 intracellular bacteria.

503 Use of engineered phages to broaden the host range [137], conversion from
504 lysogenic phages to lytic forms [138,139], expressing cell-penetrating peptides [95]
505 and incorporate enzybiotics such as endolysins [140] and phage encoded cell wall
506 degrading enzymes into their genomes have been shown to be effective *in vitro*,
507 which have paved a way for future opportunities . For instance, Xu et al reported
508 enhanced internalization of T7 phage by mammalian cells when human
509 immunodeficiency virus type 1 TAT peptide was present on its surface [141]. The
510 authors reported 2-log orders higher uptake of modified phage in mammalian cells
511 (kidney epithelial cells) compared to T7 not modified with TAT peptide [141]. In
512 another instance, increased internalization of engineered M13 was reported by HeLa
513 cells [142]. M13 was genetically engineered to express an integrin binding peptide
514 (RGD) on the major viral coat proteins. The engineered phages demonstrated a 4-
515 fold increase in uptake by HeLa cells compared to wild-type phages [142]. Dedrick et
516 al. engineered a lytic derivative of phage ZoeJ by precisely removing the repressor
517 gene identified as gene 45 which can efficiently kill *M. abscessus* (GD01) [63]. Using
518 a cocktail of engineered phages (Muddy, BPs33 Δ HTH-HRM10, and ZoeJ Δ 45) the
519 authors reported effective killing of infectious *M. abscessus* strain [63]. Phages can
520 also be genetically engineered to endure acidic environments encountered *in vivo* by
521 displaying phospholipids on the phage capsid [143]. pH-responsive biopolymers like
522 Eudragit®S100 have been shown to protect phage activity from acid damage at pH

523 as low as 2.0 compared to free phages [144]. Interestingly, phages were conditioned
524 for maximum release (70%) in a simulated intestinal fluid with pH 7.0 compared to
525 40% at pH 5.0 [144]. The use of pH-sensitive biopolymers as a carrier for intracellular
526 phage delivery may result in specific release of phages within specialized organelles
527 and facilitate the killing of bacteria residing within these organelles. Endocytosis
528 mediated uptake of particles sometimes results in endosomal compartmentalization
529 and renders it inaccessible to the pathogen residing in the cytoplasm. Cationic
530 polymers containing several secondary and tertiary amines are known to induce
531 osmotic stress by entrapment of protons in the endosome membrane, a phenomenon
532 known as “proton sponge effect”. Trapped protons increase the membrane potential
533 that causes an influx of chloride ions into the endosome. This raises the osmotic
534 pressure which eventually ruptures the endosome and facilitates cytosolic delivery
535 [145,146]. These mechanisms could be utilized for efficient delivery of phage-loaded
536 particles directly into a specific intracellular site of infection.

537 **7. Concluding remarks**

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539 Phages are natural predators of bacteria and serve as excellent therapeutic agents
540 against various bacterial infections. Although phage therapy has been well practiced
541 against several bacterial infections, studies focusing on the therapeutic efficacy of
542 phages against intracellular infection have remained largely unexplored. By the virtue
543 of residing within a specific intracellular compartment, these intracellular pathogens
544 are challenging to treat. With rising concern over antibiotic resistance, phage therapy
545 could be an alternative approach to reduce such bacterial infections. In this review, we
546 have focussed on discussing the efficacy of phage delivery against intracellular
547 infection. An overview of studies that have used phages in free and encapsulated form
548 has been highlighted. Liposomes and biopolymers could serve as an efficient carrier

549 to deliver phages into the intracellular milieu. Mechanisms to increase the uptake of
550 phages by the infected mammalian cells are needed to enhance the therapeutic
551 efficacy of phages against intracellular infection. Additionally, the challenges and
552 future strategies pertaining to intracellular phage therapy has also been discussed.
553 These challenges provide ample scope for research to develop phages as a
554 therapeutic approach towards combating intracellular bacterial infection.

555 **8. Acknowledgements:**

556 We acknowledge all members of Drug Delivery Laboratory at Indian Institute of
557 Science, Bangalore, for their input regarding the clarity and editing of the manuscript.
558 Rachit Agarwal acknowledges the funding received from Ramanujan fellowship
559 (SB/S2/RJN-036/2017, Department of Science and Technology, India), Bill & Melinda
560 Gates Foundation (OPP1210498), Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore and Mr.
561 Lakshmi Narayanan. Financial support by Department of Biotechnology (DBT-
562 Research Associate), India and Science and Engineering Research Board (N-PDF,
563 PDF/2020/000290), India to Avijit Goswami is also acknowledged. Pallavi Raj Sharma
564 acknowledges fellowship support from Department of Biotechnology, India (DBT-JRF,
565 DBT/2017/IISc/941).

566 **Disclosure statement**

567 The authors declare no conflict of interest

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Table 1: List of intracellular bacteria, their mechanism of entry, target cell and phages available in literature

Sr. No	Intracellular Bacteria	Mechanism of entry	Target Cell	Phages available	Reference
1	<i>Mycobacterium abscessus</i>	Receptor mediated endocytosis	Macrophages	phiT46-1	[147]
2	<i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i>	Receptor mediated endocytosis	Macrophages	D29, TM4, DS6A	[148-150]
3	<i>Shigella flexneri</i>	Trigger mode*	Epithelial cells	Sfin-1, Sf11-Sf25	[151,152]
4	<i>Shigella dysenteriae</i>	Trigger mode*	Epithelial cells	SF-9	[153]
5	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	Zipper Mode	Epithelial cells	A511, P100, LMP1, LMP7	[154-156]
6	<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	Trigger mode*	Epithelial cells/Macrophages	P22-B1, P22, PBST10, PBST13, PBST32, and PBST 35	[157]
7	<i>Yersinia Pestis</i>	Zipper Mode**	Epithelial cells	PhiA1122, Yep-Phi	[158,159]
	<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i>	Zipper Mode**	Epithelial cells	Yersinia Phage X1	[160]
8	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Zipper Mode**	Epithelial cells/Macrophages	vB_SauS-phiIPLA35 (phiIPLA35),vB_SauS-phiIPLA88 (phiIPLA88)	[161]
9	<i>Chlamydia</i>	Trigger mode*	Epithelial cells	Chp2, Chp3, φCPG1 φCPAR39 (φCpn1) and Chp4	[162]
10	<i>S. enterica</i>	Trigger mode*	Epithelial cells/Macrophages	ZCSE2	[163]
11	<i>E coli</i>	Trigger mode*	Epithelial cells	K1F	[164]
12	<i>Mycobacterium leprae</i>	Receptor mediated endocytosis	Epithelial cells	No	
13	<i>Coxiella burnetii</i>	Trigger mode*	Epithelial cells	No	

570 *Trigger mode- A Macropinocytosis- related Process- involves type 3/4 secretion system

571 **Zipper mode- A Clathrin- and Actin- mediated Internalization Process

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Table 2: Free phages against intracellular bacterial infection

Sr No.	Intracellular pathogen targeted	Phage used for the study	Experimental Model/Cell type	Reference
1	<i>Chlamydia psittaci</i>	phiCPG1	HeLa cell	[165]
2	<i>M. tuberculosis</i>	Mycobacteriophage D29	Primary cells: mouse peritoneal macrophages	[78]
3	<i>S. aureus</i>	M ^{Sa}	Peritoneal mouse macrophages-has in vivo results also	[80]
4	<i>M. ulcerans</i>	D29	Murine footpad model	[166]
5	<i>S. aureus</i>	MR-5	Peritoneal mouse macrophages	[167]
6	<i>S. aureus</i>	vB_SauM_JS25	Bovine Mammary Epithelial Cells (MAC-T)	[76]
7	<i>B. pseudomallei</i>	C34	BALB/c mice	[81]
8	<i>E coli P5-AmpR</i>	Uncharacterized (from sewage)	MAC-T	[168]
9	<i>S. typhimurium</i> KCCM40253 ATCC19585 ATCC19585 CCARM8009	P22-B1,P22,PBST10 PBST13,PBST32,PB ST35	<i>in vitro</i> effect on bacteria	[169]
10	H37Rv (virulent strain of mycobacteria)	D29	Peritoneal mouse macrophages (RAW 264.7)	[79]
11	<i>E. coli</i>	K1F	Urinary bladder epithelial cell line, T24 (HTB-4)	[75]
12	<i>M. abscessus</i>	Muddy, BPs, ZoeJ (genetically engineered)	A 15-year-old patient	[63]
13	<i>E. coli</i> strain EV36	K1F	human cerebral microvascular endothelial cells (hCMEC)	[170]
14	<i>S. aureus</i>	PP1493, PP1815, and PP1957	MG63 osteoblastic Cells	[83]
15	<i>Salmonella spp</i>	SR ϕ 1	HepG2 cells	[95]

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Table 3: Carrier mediated intracellular phage delivery

Sr No.	Intracellular pathogen targeted	Phage used for the study	Experimental Model/Cell type	Reference
1	<i>M. tuberculosis/M. avium</i>	Mycobacteriophage TM4 (Adsorbed on <i>M. smegmatis</i>)	Mouse peritoneal macrophage cell line, RAW 264.7	[84]
2	<i>M. avium</i>	TM4 (Adsorbed on <i>M. smegmatis</i>)	Female C57BL/6 black mice	[85]
3	<i>M. tuberculosis</i>	Phage λeyfp + Mycobacteriophage TM4 (Liposomes)	Human macrophage cell line (THP-1)	[131]
4	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	KPO1K2 (Liposomes)	Peritoneal mouse macrophages	[90]
5	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	KØ1, KØ2, KØ3, KØ4 and KØ5 Isolated from sewage (Liposomes)	Male BALB/C mice	[91]
6	<i>Methicillin Resistant Staphylococcus aureus</i>	MR-5 MR-10 (Liposomes)	Female BALB/C mice	[171]

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601 **Table 4 Recent phage therapy clinical trials**

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Sr No.	NCT number	Pathogen/Infection	Phage/ Cocktail	Phase of the study	Reference
1	NCT02664740 not yet recruiting	<i>S. aureus</i> and MRSA/ Diabetic Foot Ulcer mono-infections	Not mentioned	Phase 1,2	[172]
2	NCT04287478 not yet recruiting	<i>E. coli</i> and <i>K. pneumoniae</i> / Urinary Tract Infections	Personalized cocktail	Phase 1,2	[172]
3	NCT04323475 not yet recruiting	<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>P. aeruginosa</i> , or <i>K. pneumonia</i> / Second degree burn wounds	Phage Cocktail-SPK	Phase 1	[172]
4	NCT03808103 recruiting	Adherent Invasive <i>E. coli</i> / Patients with Crohn's disease	EcoActive	Phase 1,2	[172]
5	NCT04191148 recruiting	<i>E. coli</i> / Lower urinary tract infections	LBP-Ec01	Phase 1	[172]
6	NCT02116010	<i>E. coli</i> and <i>P. aeruginosa</i> / Burn wound infections	Described in [173]	Phase 1,2	[174]
7	NCT03140085	Uropathogens/ Urinary tract infections	PYO phage	Phase 2/3	[175]
8	ACTRN1261600002482	<i>S. aureus</i> / Chronic Rhinosinusitis	AB-SA01	Phase 1	[176]
9	NCT02757755	Healthy volunteers	AB-SA01	Phase 1	[172]
10	NCT00937274	<i>E. coli</i> / Diarrhoea	T4 phage cocktail	Phase 1	[177]

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